

FORGE (Formation of Optimized Robotic Groundtruth Examples) - A Dataset Generation Technique for Constrained Collision Environments in Inverse Kinematics Learning

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Abstract—Inverse kinematics (IK) involves determining the joint parameters of a manipulator robot that are necessary to position its end-effector at a specified position and orientation. It is a typical method of use for robot arm control, humanoid control, and industrial robots in assembly tasks, welding tasks, and trajectory control. Inverse kinematics in robotics is greatly challenged by constrained and collision-dense worlds, whereby analytical and numerical solvers conventionally result in infeasible solutions or require vast computational expense. FORGE (Formation of Optimized Robotic Groundtruth Examples), the introduced framework, is a hybrid method for the construction of robust datasets that is specifically aimed at constrained IK tasks. FORGE integrates three key components: (i) a metaheuristic optimization module that explores the solution space efficiently under joint and collision constraints, (ii) an Adam optimizer refinement module that fine-tunes solutions to achieve high-precision convergence, and (iii) a KD-tree-based nearest neighbor search module that ensures dataset consistency and efficient replication of similar configurations. The proposed framework supports modular configuration of robotic systems through Denavit–Hartenberg parameters, enabling adaptation across different manipulators. Experimental evaluations demonstrated that the FORGE framework generated large-scale, high-quality IK datasets with improved feasibility rates due to collision avoidance and reduced positional error compared to standalone metaheuristic methods. By unifying evolutionary search, gradient refinement, and efficient data structuring, FORGE provides a scalable and extensible approach to generate highly quality datasets for inverse kinematics learning environments with constrained collision.

Index Terms—Constrained Environment, Metaheuristic Algorithm, Inverse Kinematics, Dataset Generation, KD Trees

I. INTRODUCTION

Inverse kinematics (IK) refers to finding the parameters of a robot’s joints for a given desired end-effector position and orientation. It finds application in controlling manipulators so that a tool [1], [2], gripper [3], [4], or limb [5]–[7] touches a target point in space for precise orientation. Key difficulties in kinematics involve multi-linearity, multiple [8], zero, or ambiguous valid solutions, and large computation for redundant, constrained robotic systems [9]. Learning inverse

kinematics (IK) for robotic manipulators is a central task of robotics, which finds application in motion planning [10], [11] and control [12]. Classical analytical and numerical solvers of front-end kinematics usually fail under high degrees of freedom of environments [13], redundancy [14], and constraints of a workspace [15]. Data-based approaches, and specifically deep learning [16], have been successful for solving such difficulties. The performance of such models, however, significantly depends on how good and how diverse the data is for their training.

Generating high-quality IK datasets becomes much harder when robots have a high DOF (Degree of Freedom) or operate in environments filled with obstacles like boxes, spheres, or cylinders. In these situations, the robot must not only reach its target point but also move safely without colliding with anything. Simple random sampling often produces many invalid or blocked positions, while uniform sampling wastes effort on areas the robot can’t even reach — both leading to poor learning and weak generalization. A good dataset design solves this by capturing the robot’s full range of motion, covering joint limits and diverse poses without unnecessary repetition. Clean, balanced, and realistic data help the model learn smooth, collision-free movements, while good preprocessing and normalization make training more stable and reliable.

To address these challenges, the **FORGE** (*Formation of Optimized Robotic Groundtruth Examples*) framework was proposed, a modular framework for generating evolutionarily optimized datasets tailored for learning inverse kinematics in constrained collision environments with multiple obstacles. FORGE integrates metaheuristic algorithms with the Adam optimizer to produce datasets that minimize angular deviation, measured as the Euclidean distance between initial and final joint angles, and end-effector positional error, calculated as the Euclidean distance between the target position and the end-effector’s actual position, while ensuring collision avoidance. The framework supports robot models defined via importable

DH (Denavit-Hartenberg) parameters and environment setups that describe obstacles. Dataset generation is accelerated through parallel multithreading, with each CPU core independently handling the creation of a complete datapoint, enabling efficient and scalable dataset production.

Experiments with four different robotic arms, three of which are industrial-grade,

- FANUC M-20iA (Industrial)
- Kawasaki BX200L (Industrial)
- KUKA YouBot
- TM5-700 (Industrial)

demonstrate that datasets generated by FORGE lead to significant improvements in the training stability, accuracy, and generalization capability of datasets for IK learning. By focusing on realistic, constraint-aware scenarios, FORGE provides a practical tool for enabling strong data-driven IK in real-world applications where finding a real-time dataset is the biggest challenge. FORGE facilitates the generation of high-quality synthetic datasets for inverse kinematics.

Key highlights of the paper are:

- Proposed FORGE, a modular hybrid framework for generating high-quality inverse kinematics datasets in constrained, collision-prone environments.
- Combined metaheuristic optimization with the Adam optimizer to balance global exploration and local precision, achieving sub-millimeter accuracy on multiple robotic platforms.
- Used a KD-tree nearest neighbour search to efficiently retrieve feasible joint configurations, improving data consistency and reducing generation time.
- Supported different robot models through Denavit–Hartenberg parameters and realistic obstacle-based scenes, enabling flexible and constraint-aware simulations.
- Implemented multithreaded execution for scalable dataset generation, where each core independently produces collision-free data points.
- Experiments on four robots—FANUC M-20iA, Kawasaki BX200L, KUKA YouBot, and TM5-700—showed strong performance gains in feasibility, stability, and accuracy.
- Found that Social Group Optimization and Particle Swarm Optimization delivered the most stable results after gradient refinement, while KD-tree queries were several orders faster than metaheuristic solvers.
- Periodic KD-tree rebuilding every 200 insertions offered the best runtime efficiency during large-scale dataset generation.
- Overall, FORGE provides a scalable and precise approach for data-driven inverse kinematics learning and can be extended toward neural network–based solvers.

The paper is structured as follows: Section II (Related Work) highlights recent advancements in inverse kinematics using optimization-based methods. Section III (Problem Definition) formalizes the constrained IK problem, defines the fitness function considering the weighted sum of angular

deviation, positional accuracy, and collisions, and illustrates the role of environmental constraints such as obstacles in the form of boxes, spheres, and cylinders. Section IV (FORGE: The Proposed Framework) introduces the dataset generation framework, detailing its modular design whose components are robot model handler, scene and collision manager, nearest neighbour engine, etc. Section V (Analysis and Discussion) evaluates the accuracy, solution distributions, algorithmic performance, and probabilistic guarantees of the proposed approach. Finally, Section VI (Conclusion and Future Work) summarizes the contributions and outlines potential research directions.

II. RELATED WORK

Inverse kinematics solved through optimization has a long history, but recent years have seen rapid progress with the integration of learning-based algorithms. This section reviews recent advancements in inverse kinematics achieved through metaheuristic algorithms, classical optimization approaches, and learning algorithms.

To start with, Deng et al. [17] showed that Adaptive PSO can effectively solve the inverse kinematics of multi-DOF manipulators. It accurately computed joint angles for a 6-DOF manipulator (position and orientation) and a 7-DOF manipulator (position), outperforming other PSO variants that struggled with the same tasks. By using forward kinematics, the method works for any manipulator, since the pose matrix structure is consistent across different DH parameters. Unlike simpler approaches that consider only the end-effector position, this method handles both position and orientation, delivering precise results even for complex objectives.

A project-based paper by Li et al. [18] tackled the inverse kinematics of a 7-DOF redundant robotic arm on a mobile agricultural robot by proposing a novel differential evolution–based method. The approach incorporated a random change crossover and specially designed boundary processing to avoid joint limits, while simultaneously evaluating position and posture errors to ensure solution quality. Only DH parameters [19] were required for calculations, just like the approach discussed in this paper. The method was validated through single-point and repetitive simulation tests, demonstrating high precision and efficiency, and its scalability allows extension to manipulators with higher DOF, proving its effectiveness for real-world robotic tasks. Similarly, this paper conducts reproducibility and repetitive simulation tests to evaluate the accuracy, stability, and efficiency of the proposed method under various conditions, ensuring that the results are consistent and reliable.

In the paper by Mrabet et al. [20], they compared four metaheuristic algorithms, Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) [21], Mayfly Optimization (MFO) [22], Stochastic Paint Optimization Algorithm (SPOA) [23], and Ant Lion Optimizer (ALO) [24], for solving inverse kinematics across three robot types: a 4-DOF SCARA, a 6-DOF ABB IRB 1600, and a dual-arm Motoman SDA20D. Each algorithm was tested on 30 random target poses using a unified objective that minimized

position and orientation errors. The Mayfly Optimization Algorithm delivered the highest accuracy, especially for complex manipulators, though it required more computation time. ACO and SPOA achieved faster results with only minor accuracy loss, while ALO struggled with orientation in higher-DOF systems. The study also proposed a consistent benchmarking framework and emphasized that no single algorithm fits all robots, highlighting the trade-off between precision and efficiency in metaheuristic-based IK solvers.

In the paper by Abdor-Sierra et al. [25] conducted a comparative study of metaheuristic methods applied to resolve the inverse kinematics (IK) of redundant robot manipulators, with a special interest in the UR5 (6-DOF) and Motoman SIA20D (7-DOF). Two optimization problems were defined: IK of end-effector position only and IK of complete pose (position and orientation), the latter of which was the primary contribution. Using the Denavit–Hartenberg convention of the forward kinematics, Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) [26], and their variant versions (QPSO, SCAPSO, IPSO), Differential Evolution (DE) [27] versions, Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) [28], Firefly Algorithm (FA) [29], Grey Wolf Optimizer (GWO) [30], Cuckoo Search (CS) [31], Harmony Search (HS) [32], and others were evaluated. Algorithms were each tested with 30 experiments with 50 randomly generated target poses, with optimum solutions assessed in terms of execution time and stability. Results were presented that optimum success rates were obtained with PSO, IPSO, SCAPSO, QPSO, and DE/rand/1/bin with SCAPSO having the quickest converging behavior. Conversely, ABC, HS, FA, and GWO could not regularly approach optimum solutions with a tendency towards bad exploitation and high computational time. It was concluded from the research that while problem-dependent behavior of the problem was proven with DE versions, hybridized and advanced versions of PSO methods generated reliable and stable solutions and are therefore proposed as the best metaheuristics for use with IK problems of redundant manipulators.

As for the study of post-processing using non-metaheuristic algorithms, perhaps outside the context of inverse kinematics, in the paper by Brociek et al. [33], they tackled the problem of computed tomography reconstruction [34] using incomplete datasets, focusing on detecting defects or major structural changes within an object. The defects were modeled as polygons and reconstructed using circular approximations. To address this, the study developed a hybrid algorithm that combined metaheuristic and deterministic search methods, merging the exploration ability of algorithms like Artificial Bee Colony and Jellyfish Search [35] with the post-processing refinement efficiency of Hooke–Jeeves [36], [37] and Nelder–Mead [38], [39]. Experimental results showed that the hybrid approach not only handled the reconstruction task effectively but also outperformed a standalone multi-agent metaheuristic algorithm, delivering faster and more accurate results, allowing the development of similar algorithms for inverse kinematics in the current paper, where post-processing would be offloaded to the Adam optimizer after global exploration by metaheuristics.

Now coming to generating multiple solutions for IK, in

the paper by Ames et al. [40] presented IKFlow, an inverse kinematics solver for redundant robots that generated fast, accurate, and diverse solutions by modeling the solution space as a distribution over joint poses using deep generative models [41]. Unlike the approach in the present study, their method produced multiple solutions for the same query, although insights from their distribution-based analysis remained relevant. Experiments demonstrated that IKFlow could generate hundreds to thousands of solutions in milliseconds, with average errors of only a few millimeters in translation and less than 1.5 degrees in rotation. These results indicated that IKFlow was highly effective for 7+ DOF manipulators and could support complex robotic tasks requiring redundancy or flexibility.

As for Deep learning research in this field, Rice et al. [42] showed that for the 6-DOF ABB IRB 7600 manipulator, most Fusion IK [43] variants performed similarly, except for the exploitative iterative version, which was slower across all metrics. Network inference was identified as the most time-consuming part, especially for iterative approaches that repeatedly process values through the network. On the simulated 20-DOF robot, the iterative Fusion IK variant was notably more effective, reducing move time by 14% compared to Bio IK and achieving a 100% success rate after a 1000 ms timeout. These findings suggest that the iterative version of Fusion IK has strong potential even without additional tuning. Future work could explore whether deep neural networks alone could directly generate IK solutions or whether the method could be applied to other optimization problems, highlighting the flexibility and promise of the Fusion IK approach for high-DOF manipulators.

As for possible future work for FORGE involving trajectory optimization, López-Muñoz [44] presented a metaheuristic-based approach to solve the inverse kinematics of serial robots and to identify end-effector trajectories using differential evolution (DE). The method introduced a biased initialization that accounted for the robot’s previous posture and the distance between the current and initial effector positions along a trajectory. For the Fanuc M-200 robot, this dynamic weighting improved both the mean error (11.02 vs. 40.40 for a fixed approach) and variance, achieving approximately 0.22 mm per trajectory point. Additionally, the approach combined metaheuristics with Fourier series [45] to generate parametric models of effector motion, achieving errors below 0.22 radians across the entire trajectory. This made the method accurate, robust, and directly applicable for industrial trajectory planning.

In summary, prior research on inverse kinematics has explored a variety of approaches, ranging from metaheuristic algorithms to deep learning-based solvers and hybrid methods. Adaptive PSO and its variants [17], [20], [25] demonstrated reliable performance for multi-DOF manipulators, while differential evolution-based methods [18] provided precise solutions for redundant arms with reproducibility across simulations. Hybrid approaches [33] illustrated the benefits of combining exploration and refinement, achieving robust and accurate results in complex tasks. Distribution-based solvers like IKFlow [40] highlighted the potential of generating di-

verse, high-quality solutions quickly, whereas deep learning methods such as Fusion IK [42] showed efficiency gains for high-DOF robots through neural network-guided optimization. Finally, trajectory optimization methods using metaheuristics and differential evolution [44] offered accurate parametric models for end-effector motion, which could be leveraged in FORGE to generate high-quality datasets and plan robust robot trajectories in the future. Collectively, these studies provide valuable insights into algorithm design, solution accuracy, and scalability, guiding the development of more reproducible, efficient, and flexible IK solutions for complex robotic systems.

III. PROBLEM DEFINITION

This section outlines the fundamental components required to define the inverse kinematics problem. It contains two subsections, Section III-A (Constrained Inverse Kinematics Problem) and Section III-B (Formulation of constraint environment).

A. Constrained Inverse Kinematics Problem

The goal of this work is to generate high-quality datasets for learning inverse kinematics (IK) in constrained environments populated with obstacles such as boxes, spheres, and cylinders. As a first step, this requires designing an efficient fitness function to evaluate the validity of a datapoint. To begin with, each data point in the dataset consists of an initial joint configuration,

- θ_{init} , set to zero for all joint angles.
- \mathbf{p}_{target} , target end-effector position.
- θ_{final} , optimized joint configuration that reaches the target while avoiding collisions and minimizing motion-related costs.

Given a robotic manipulator with n degrees of freedom, a candidate joint configuration can be represented as $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^n$, where each element corresponds to an individual joint angle. Using the manipulator's forward kinematics model, the corresponding end-effector position in Cartesian space is denoted by $\mathbf{p}_\theta \in \mathbb{R}^3$. This mapping establishes the relationship between the robot's joint space and its task space, forming the mathematical foundation for solving the inverse kinematics problem, where the goal is to determine the optimal θ that positions the end-effector at a desired target location.

For calculations for the positional error segment in the fitness function, we take the function $d(\theta)$ using (1) and calculate initial distance d_i , by setting the input parameter as θ_{init} , and final distance d_f , as defined for a joint configuration θ_{final} .

$$d = \|\mathbf{p}_\theta - \mathbf{p}_{target}\|_2 \quad (1)$$

Therefore positional error π would be the normalised distance between the end-effector's current position and the desired target, calculated relative to the initial distance d_i . If $d_i = 0$, the positional error is defined to be zero; otherwise, it is given by (2).

$$\pi = \begin{cases} 0 & , \text{ if } d_i = 0 \\ \frac{d_f}{d_i} & , \text{ otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The raw angular error α_{raw} is defined in (3), which is computed as the Euclidean distance between the final joint angles θ_{final} and the initial joint angles θ_{init} .

$$\alpha_{raw} = \|\theta_{final} - \theta_{init}\|_2 \quad (3)$$

The raw angular error is normalized using α_{max} , which denotes the maximum achievable angular displacement for an n -DOF manipulator, assuming each joint can rotate freely within the range $[-180^\circ, 180^\circ]$. Accordingly, α_{max} is computed as $\sqrt{n \cdot 180^2}$, and the normalized angular deviation is expressed in (4).

$$\alpha = \frac{\alpha_{raw}}{\alpha_{max}} \quad (4)$$

The final fitness function to be minimized is shown in (5).

$$f(\theta) = \begin{cases} \lambda \cdot \pi + (1 - \lambda) \cdot \alpha, & \text{ if } \theta \text{ is collision-free} \\ \infty, & \text{ if } \theta \text{ results in collision} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

A collision is assigned an infinite (or sufficiently large) penalty value, ensuring that such configurations are effectively excluded from consideration in the final solution. Here, λ is a weighting factor that balances positional accuracy and angular efficiency, which for the scope of this paper is taken to be 0.5. A configuration is assigned infinite fitness if it leads to any collision with environmental obstacles.

B. Formulation of constraint environment

To demonstrate how collision constraints are incorporated into the inverse kinematics problem, the environment is illustrated with pseudocode for collision detection and graphical examples of robot-obstacle interactions. The pseudocode highlights the procedure for verifying whether a candidate joint configuration is feasible, while the figures visually distinguish between colliding and collision-free configurations.

1) *Line Cube Intersection*: Algorithm 1 checks whether a line segment intersects an axis-aligned bounding box (AABB) by computing parametric entry and exit values along each axis. The line is expressed as $p(t) = p_1 + t(p_2 - p_1)$ with $t \in [0, 1]$. For each axis, the algorithm computes the interval where the line lies inside the box and updates the global intersection interval $[t_{min}, t_{max}]$. If at any point $t_{min} > t_{max}$, the line misses the box; otherwise, an intersection is detected.

Algorithm 1 Line–AABB Intersection

```
0: function LINECUBEINTERSECTS( $p_1, p_2, \min, \max$ )
0:    $t_{\min} \leftarrow 0, t_{\max} \leftarrow 1$ 
0:    $dir \leftarrow p_2 - p_1$ 
0:   for each axis  $i \in \{x, y, z\}$  do
0:     if  $|dir[i]| < \varepsilon$  then
0:       if  $p_1[i] < \min[i] \vee p_1[i] > \max[i]$  then
0:         return false
0:       end if
0:     else
0:        $inv\_dir \leftarrow 1/dir[i]$ 
0:        $t_1 \leftarrow (\min[i] - p_1[i]) \cdot inv\_dir$ 
0:        $t_2 \leftarrow (\max[i] - p_1[i]) \cdot inv\_dir$ 
0:       if  $t_1 > t_2$  then
0:          $swap(t_1, t_2)$ 
0:       end if
0:        $t_{\min} \leftarrow \max(t_{\min}, t_1)$ 
0:        $t_{\max} \leftarrow \min(t_{\max}, t_2)$ 
0:       if  $t_{\min} > t_{\max}$  then
0:         return false
0:       end if
0:     end if
0:   end for
0:   return true
0: end function=0
```

2) *Line Sphere Intersection*: Algorithm 2 determines whether a line segment intersects a sphere by solving the quadratic equation derived from substituting the line equation $p(t) = p_1 + t(p_2 - p_1)$ into the sphere equation $\|p - c\|^2 = r^2$. The discriminant $\Delta = b^2 - 4ac$ is used to check if a real intersection exists. If $\Delta < 0$, no intersection occurs. Otherwise, the solutions t_1, t_2 are tested for validity within the segment domain $[0, 1]$ to confirm whether the segment actually intersects the sphere.

Algorithm 2 Line–Sphere Intersection

```
0: function LINESPHEREINTERSECT( $p_1, p_2, c, r$ )
0:    $d \leftarrow p_2 - p_1$  {line direction}
0:    $f \leftarrow p_1 - c$  {vector from sphere center to  $p_1$ }
0:    $a \leftarrow d \cdot d$ 
0:    $b \leftarrow 2(f \cdot d)$ 
0:    $c \leftarrow (f \cdot f) - r^2$ 
0:    $\Delta \leftarrow b^2 - 4ac$ 
0:   if  $\Delta < 0$  then return false
0:   end if
0:    $t_1 \leftarrow \frac{-b - \sqrt{\Delta}}{2a}$ 
0:    $t_2 \leftarrow \frac{-b + \sqrt{\Delta}}{2a}$ 
0:   if  $0 \leq t_1 \leq 1 \vee 0 \leq t_2 \leq 1$  then return true
0:   elsereturn false
0:   end if
0: end function=0
```

Algorithm 3 Line–Cylinder Intersection (x-axis aligned)

```
0: function LINECYLINDERINTERECT( $p_1, p_2, base, h, r$ )
0:    $axis \leftarrow (1, 0, 0)$ 
0:    $d \leftarrow p_2 - p_1$  {line direction}
0:    $m \leftarrow p_1 - base$  {relative to cylinder base}
0:    $dot_d \leftarrow d \cdot axis$ 
0:    $dot_m \leftarrow m \cdot axis$ 
0:    $n \leftarrow d - dot_d \cdot axis$ 
0:    $o \leftarrow m - dot_m \cdot axis$ 
0:    $a \leftarrow n \cdot n$ 
0:    $b \leftarrow 2(n \cdot o)$ 
0:    $c \leftarrow (o \cdot o) - r^2$ 
0:    $\Delta \leftarrow b^2 - 4ac$ 
0:   if  $\Delta < 0 \vee a = 0$  then return false
0:   end if
0:    $t_1 \leftarrow \frac{-b - \sqrt{\Delta}}{2a}$ 
0:    $t_2 \leftarrow \frac{-b + \sqrt{\Delta}}{2a}$ 
0:   for each  $t \in \{t_1, t_2\}$  do
0:     if  $0 \leq t \leq 1$  then
0:        $p \leftarrow p_1 + t \cdot d$ 
0:        $proj \leftarrow (p - base) \cdot axis$ 
0:       if  $0 \leq proj \leq h$  then return true
0:       end if
0:     end if
0:   end for
0:   return false
0: end function=0
```

3) *Line Cylinder Intersection*: Algorithm 3 detects intersections between a line segment and a finite cylinder aligned with the x -axis. It first projects out the axial component of the line direction and reduces the problem to checking intersection within the circular cross-section in the yz -plane. The quadratic equation $at^2 + bt + c = 0$ is solved for possible intersection points, and candidate solutions $t \in [0, 1]$ are evaluated. For each valid solution, the projection along the cylinder axis is checked to ensure it lies within the finite cylinder height, thus confirming intersection.

IV. FORGE: THE PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

A. Overview of FORGE

FORGE (Formation of Optimized Robotic Groundtruth Examples) is a framework designed to generate high-quality datasets for industrial robots, particularly those with rotational joints. Its primary objective is to identify joint configurations that minimize positional error and angular displacement while ensuring collision-free operation. These datasets are well-suited for downstream tasks such as training neural networks, symbolic regressors, and other supervised learning models.

At its core, FORGE employs a fitness-based optimization approach that balances three objectives: minimizing end-effector positional error, minimizing angular deviation from a reference posture, and avoiding collisions with the environment or the robot itself. The current implementation supports serial manipulators defined using standard Denavit–Hartenberg (DH) parameters.

The framework is modular and extensible, allowing easy integration of new robot models, cost functions, and optimization algorithms as well as new features for upgrading the framework. It supports environment-aware simulations using user-defined JSON scenes, enabling the generation of feasible joint-space solutions even in cluttered or constrained workspaces.

By automating large-scale, collision-aware, and precision-focused dataset generation, FORGE accelerates the development and benchmarking of intelligent inverse kinematics solvers, motion planning strategies, and learning-based control systems. A flowchart of the entire framework can be seen in Fig 1.

B. Modular Structure of FORGE

FORGE is built on a modular, multithreaded architecture designed for flexibility, extensibility, and scalability. It is particularly suited for tasks involving inverse kinematics, joint-space optimization, and collision-aware motion generation, with support for both global and local search strategies.

The key components of FORGE are:

- **Robot Model Handler:** Parses DH parameters to define kinematic chains and compute analytical forward kinematics. It also enforces joint limits and generates transformation matrices for positional and angular evaluation.
- **Scene and Collision Manager:** Loads workspace descriptions from JSON files (as shown in Section III-B) and supports basic 3D primitives such as boxes, spheres, and cylinders. Collision detection is handled via fast, thread-safe intersection routines, including AABB and ray-shape tests.
- **Nearest Neighbour Engine:** The nearest neighbour engine utilizes a KD Tree [46] to efficiently search for the n closest points in three-dimensional space. Its components include:
 - *Generator:* Constructs a balanced KD Tree from an input CSV file, if one has been pre-generated.
 - *Insert Function:* Adds a newly generated point to the KD Tree without enforcing balance constraints.
 - *Query:* Given a 3D position and an integer n , this function retrieves the n nearest points using a fixed-size priority queue, pushing and popping at each level of the tree during the search.
 - *Balance Score:* Evaluates the structural balance of the KD Tree using Eq. 6, where β is the balance score, and h_{\max} and h_{\min} denote the maximum and minimum tree heights, respectively.
$$\beta = 1 - \frac{|h_{\max} - h_{\min}|}{\max(h_{\max}, h_{\min})} \quad (6)$$
 - *Rebuild:* Reconstructs the KD Tree periodically, or whenever the balance score falls below a predefined threshold. This ensures improved query efficiency by maintaining a structurally well-balanced tree.
- **Optimization Engine:** Supports a dual-strategy backend:

Fig. 1. Flowchart of FORGE framework

- *KD Tree Search*: The target point is first evaluated to get the n nearest candidate solutions. If the closest solution lies within a 100 mm vicinity of the target, the process directly proceeds to the Adam Optimizer. Otherwise, the n nearest solutions are passed into the metaheuristic population for global optimization.
- *Metaheuristics*: Algorithms like Genetic Algorithm (GA) [47], Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) [48], and Teaching–Learning–Based Optimization (TLBO) [49] perform global, gradient-free exploration of complex, high-dimensional joint spaces.
- *Adam Optimizer*: Numerical gradients are used for local refinement, enabling high-precision convergence when the objective function is smooth or differentiable.
- **Multithreaded Execution Manager**: Parallelizes fitness evaluation and optimization runs across multiple CPU cores. Each thread handles a separate end-effector target, using thread-safe data structures and collision checks to ensure consistency and speed.
- **Data Logging and Export**: Records joint configurations, fitness values, target positions, collision status, and runtime metrics. Results are exported in CSV format for integration with machine learning workflows or for benchmarking and visualization.

This structure enables researchers to adapt FORGE for different robot types, objective formulations, and optimization pipelines with minimal effort. Its combination of hybrid optimization and concurrent execution makes FORGE a robust platform for generating high-fidelity robotic ground-truth data at scale.

V. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the justification for FORGE’s design choices, followed by an in-depth analysis and discussion of the results. FORGE was implemented in C++ and compiled using GCC version 14.2.1, with all experiments executed under this setup. Statistical analyses of the experimental results were conducted in Python 3.12. Testing was carried out on a system equipped with an Intel Core i7-1255U processor, 16 GB of RAM, running Ubuntu 22.04.5 LTS.

The robots used for the study of this framework were KUKA YouBot, FANUC M-20iA, Kawasaki BX200L, and TM5-700. The corresponding Denavit–Hartenberg (DH) parameters for each manipulator are summarized in Table III, Table I, Table II, and Table IV, respectively. These parameters serve as the mathematical foundation for forward and inverse kinematics modeling within the proposed framework.

A. Metaheuristic Accuracy and Gradient Refinement

Metaheuristic algorithms, including Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) [48], Genetic Algorithm (GA) [47], Social Group Optimization (SGO) [50], Teaching–Learning Based Optimization (TLBO) [49], and Differential Evolution (DE) [51], are well-suited for global exploration in robotic inverse kinematics. They efficiently navigate high-dimensional configuration spaces and avoid poor local minima, providing diverse

TABLE I
DH PARAMETERS OF FANUC M-20iA

Joint	a (mm)	d (mm)	α (deg)
1	150	525	-90
2	790	0	180
3	150	0	90
4	0	860	-90
5	0	0	90
6	0	100	0

TABLE II
DH PARAMETERS OF KAWASAKI BX200L

Joint	a (mm)	d (mm)	α (deg)
1	0	746	90
2	1250	0	0
3	250	0	90
4	0	1000	-90
5	0	0	90
6	0	200	0

TABLE III
DH PARAMETERS OF KUKA YouBOT

Joint	a (mm)	d (mm)	α (deg)
1	33	147	90
2	155	0	0
3	135	0	0
4	0	0	90
5	0	217.5	0

TABLE IV
DH PARAMETERS OF TM5-700

Joint	a (mm)	d (mm)	α (deg)
1	0	145.2	90
2	329	0	0
3	311.5	0	0
4	0	106	90
5	0	106	-90
6	0	113.2	0

candidate solutions. Nevertheless, due to their stochastic and exploratory nature, the raw outputs often remain near-optimal, exhibiting residual positional errors even after convergence.

To enhance precision, a gradient-based post-processing step using the Adam optimizer was applied for all four robots. While the metaheuristics identified promising global regions, Adam exploited local gradient information to fine-tune the solutions. This hybrid approach combined the strengths of both paradigms: robust global search from metaheuristics and precise local convergence from gradient descent.

The detailed results are summarized in Tables V–VIII, which report the mean positional accuracy and runtime (mean \pm standard deviation) over 1000 independent runs. The corresponding convergence behavior is illustrated in Figures 2–5, where the positional errors of different metaheuristics after Adam refinement are displayed on a logarithmic scale. Across the Fanuc M20iA, Kawasaki BX200L, and TM5-700, PSO, SGO, and DE consistently achieved sub-centimeter accuracy after GD refinement, with average errors below 1 mm. TLBO showed moderate improvements, generally converging within

Fig. 2. Positional error of different metaheuristic algorithms after Adam refinement, displayed on a logarithmic scale (Fanuc M20iA).

the 10–30 mm range, which suggests comparatively weaker exploration capabilities. Among these, SGO demonstrated particularly strong and stable performance across all robots. Its group-based learning mechanism allowed it to balance exploration and exploitation effectively, resulting in smooth convergence curves and relatively low variance compared to PSO and DE. This indicates that SGO not only identified high-quality solutions but also did so with consistency, making it one of the most reliable metaheuristics in this study.

In contrast, GA exhibited both poor accuracy and extreme variability across all robots, with standard deviations comparable to or exceeding the mean, confirming its tendency to converge to poor-quality solutions prematurely. Visually, the convergence plots also highlight GA’s instability: its error curves often jitter and fluctuate far more than the other algorithms. Despite this instability, GA occasionally produced competitive solutions, indicating that while its exploratory behavior is inconsistent, it is still capable of reaching good regions of the search space under favorable conditions.

The convergence plots (Figures 2–5) clearly highlight the effect of refinement: while the metaheuristics alone provided near-optimal but scattered solutions, Adam refinement compressed the positional errors by several orders of magnitude. This hybrid strategy proved effective across all four platforms, demonstrating that while population-based algorithms excel at global exploration, gradient refinement is essential for achieving the sub-centimeter precision required in robotic inverse kinematics.

B. Analysis of Joint Angle Probability Distributions for a Fixed Target Query

To assess the behavior of various metaheuristic approaches in solving inverse kinematics, statistical analysis was conducted by adopting a static initial joint setting of $[0, 0, 0, 0, 0]$ and a target end-effector position of $[100.0, 10.0, 10.0]$. KUKA YouBot was adopted as the robot model of choice here. The joint angle output probability distributions from five different optimization approaches—the (a) Differential Evolution (DE), (b) Genetic Algorithm (GA), (c) Particle

Fig. 3. Positional error of different metaheuristic algorithms after Adam refinement, displayed on a logarithmic scale (Kawasaki BX200L).

Fig. 4. Positional error of different metaheuristic algorithms after Adam refinement, displayed on a logarithmic scale (TM5-700).

Fig. 5. Positional error of different metaheuristic algorithms after Adam refinement, displayed on a logarithmic scale (KUKA YouBot).

TABLE V

MEAN POSITIONAL ACCURACY AND RUNTIME (MEAN \pm STANDARD DEVIATION) FOR METAHEURISTICS AND GRADIENT DESCENT (GD) REFINEMENT OVER 1000 RUNS. ACCURACY IS REPORTED IN MILLIMETERS (MM), AND RUNTIME IN MILLISECONDS (MS) (FANUC M20iA).

Algorithm	Meta Acc (mm)	GD Acc (mm)	Meta Time (ms)	GD Time (ms)
Particle Swarm Optimization	8.189 \pm 5.537	0.350 \pm 1.225	65.031 \pm 5.080	1.113 \pm 0.114
Genetic Algorithm	653.265 \pm 647.735	589.263 \pm 626.638	55.787 \pm 4.925	1.103 \pm 0.107
Social Group Optimization	9.726 \pm 4.999	0.289 \pm 0.816	94.834 \pm 8.553	1.105 \pm 0.112
Teaching Learning Based Optimization	70.131 \pm 26.867	23.688 \pm 22.624	54.717 \pm 4.095	1.115 \pm 0.097
Differential Evolution	12.143 \pm 5.239	0.540 \pm 1.646	43.487 \pm 4.802	1.107 \pm 0.106

TABLE VI

MEAN POSITIONAL ACCURACY AND RUNTIME (MEAN \pm STANDARD DEVIATION) FOR METAHEURISTICS AND GRADIENT DESCENT (GD) REFINEMENT OVER 1000 RUNS. ACCURACY IS REPORTED IN MILLIMETERS (MM), AND RUNTIME IN MILLISECONDS (MS) (KAWASAKI BX200L).

Algorithm	Meta Acc (mm)	GD Acc (mm)	Meta Time (ms)	GD Time (ms)
Particle Swarm Optimization	10.945 \pm 6.614	0.273 \pm 1.293	71.055 \pm 7.629	1.168 \pm 0.126
Genetic Algorithm	887.868 \pm 913.684	802.956 \pm 887.278	62.322 \pm 7.634	1.161 \pm 0.124
Social Group Optimization	13.811 \pm 7.029	0.224 \pm 0.737	105.761 \pm 13.301	1.163 \pm 0.122
Teaching Learning Based Optimization	64.909 \pm 26.870	15.214 \pm 20.569	58.526 \pm 5.717	1.169 \pm 0.115
Differential Evolution	18.638 \pm 7.912	0.405 \pm 1.434	50.149 \pm 7.644	1.160 \pm 0.121

TABLE VII

MEAN POSITIONAL ACCURACY AND RUNTIME (MEAN \pm STANDARD DEVIATION) FOR METAHEURISTICS AND GRADIENT DESCENT (GD) REFINEMENT OVER 1000 RUNS. ACCURACY IS REPORTED IN MILLIMETERS (MM), AND RUNTIME IN MILLISECONDS (MS) (TM5-700).

Algorithm	Meta Acc (mm)	GD Acc (mm)	Meta Time (ms)	GD Time (ms)
Particle Swarm Optimization	3.775 \pm 3.039	0.125 \pm 0.581	77.130 \pm 19.823	1.117 \pm 0.361
Genetic Algorithm	285.321 \pm 244.141	251.033 \pm 235.455	67.786 \pm 18.262	1.238 \pm 0.336
Social Group Optimization	5.554 \pm 3.108	0.118 \pm 0.321	115.025 \pm 30.695	1.159 \pm 0.329
Teaching Learning Based Optimization	35.163 \pm 13.087	9.928 \pm 10.853	64.682 \pm 15.564	1.254 \pm 0.304
Differential Evolution	8.223 \pm 3.493	0.276 \pm 0.719	54.090 \pm 15.581	1.215 \pm 0.315

TABLE VIII

MEAN POSITIONAL ACCURACY AND RUNTIME (MEAN \pm STANDARD DEVIATION) FOR METAHEURISTICS AND GRADIENT DESCENT (GD) REFINEMENT OVER 1000 RUNS. ACCURACY IS REPORTED IN MILLIMETERS (MM), AND RUNTIME IN MILLISECONDS (MS) (KUKA YouBot).

Algorithm	Meta Acc (mm)	GD Acc (mm)	Meta Time (ms)	GD Time (ms)
Particle Swarm Optimization	4.490 \pm 3.805	0.243 \pm 0.938	59.275 \pm 7.257	0.784 \pm 0.164
Genetic Algorithm	174.054 \pm 174.249	150.600 \pm 165.918	54.700 \pm 7.307	0.849 \pm 0.115
Social Group Optimization	3.882 \pm 2.180	0.168 \pm 0.519	87.585 \pm 13.204	0.762 \pm 0.166
Teaching Learning Based Optimization	11.607 \pm 4.912	0.943 \pm 2.012	50.677 \pm 5.979	0.837 \pm 0.117
Differential Evolution	6.987 \pm 2.735	0.635 \pm 1.424	42.017 \pm 7.333	0.817 \pm 0.130

Swarm Optimization (PSO), (d) Social Group Optimization (SGO), and (e) Teaching–Learning Based Optimization (TLBO), for KUKA YouBot, towards a same end-effector position, was initially retrieved without adopting any nearest-neighbour structure (Fig 6). The candidate configurations in this case were assessed from repeated inverse kinematics, and retrieved distributions held stochasticity of search inherent in them. Since no structure to promote search in direction of a particular solution was provided, there was wide dispersion of angular deviation, a sign symptomatic of over-diversity of solution from bottom-level metaheuristics. The analysis based on standard deviations as well as mean angle values from all these runs are tabulated in Table IX.

In contrast, when a KD-tree was integrated into the initial population generation (Fig 7), the probability distributions became noticeably sharper and more consistent across algorithms. The KD-tree enabled rapid retrieval of neighbouring configurations from prior evaluations, reducing redundant convergence towards the target. As a result, the distributions

showed less variance, indicating that the algorithms were not only reaching the desired end-effector position more effectively but also maintaining tighter angular consistency across repeated trials. Table X presents the mean joint angles and corresponding standard deviations computed across all runs.

To test the stability of the Nearest Neighbour implementation, a circulatory trajectory was used as visual proof of concept. As can be observed in Fig. 8(a), results without Nearest Neighbour integration come across as shaky, wherein calculated inverse kinematics (IK) solutions are correct but cause abrupt shifts between consecutive configurations. This kind of behavior suggests wasteful energy consumption and redundant joint movements. As can be seen in Fig. 8(b), it is visible that implementing the Nearest Neighbour results in smooth, stable shifts in states, reducing redundant motion to a minimum. The KD-tree, therefore, adds memory to the framework and since FORGE, being a dataset generation model, is conceptualized to have objectives aligned in this manner, this aspect fits in perfectly.

Fig. 6. Probability distribution of joint angle outputs generated by five optimization algorithms (a-e) for the KUKA YouBot, targeting the same end-effector position without employing a KD-tree.

Fig. 7. Probability distribution of joint angle outputs generated by five optimization algorithms (a-e) for the KUKA YouBot, targeting the same end-effector position with KD-tree nearest neighbor search.

TABLE IX
JOINT ANGLE STATISTICS WITHOUT KD TREE (MEAN \pm STD. DEV. IN RADIAN)

Joint	PSO	GA	SGO	TLBO	DE
J1	3.24 \pm 0.10	2.01 \pm 1.88	2.10 \pm 1.53	1.83 \pm 1.89	1.89 \pm 1.56
J2	2.88 \pm 2.01	2.91 \pm 2.13	2.34 \pm 1.79	3.36 \pm 1.86	2.06 \pm 1.58
J3	2.82 \pm 0.55	3.28 \pm 2.11	2.95 \pm 1.08	2.77 \pm 1.65	2.87 \pm 1.06
J4	2.68 \pm 1.20	3.24 \pm 2.16	2.57 \pm 1.55	3.79 \pm 1.61	2.46 \pm 1.47
J5	2.99 \pm 1.18	2.33 \pm 2.22	3.02 \pm 1.92	3.02 \pm 1.96	2.64 \pm 1.74

TABLE X
JOINT ANGLE STATISTICS WITH KD TREES (MEAN \pm STD. DEV. IN RADIAN)

Joint	PSO	GA	SGO	TLBO	DE
J1	0.11 \pm 0.17	3.24 \pm 0.10	3.23 \pm 0.14	0.10 \pm 0.00	0.12 \pm 0.22
J2	2.33 \pm 0.20	0.71 \pm 0.06	0.90 \pm 0.08	2.26 \pm 0.13	2.10 \pm 0.21
J3	3.69 \pm 0.05	3.44 \pm 0.01	3.33 \pm 0.03	2.36 \pm 0.15	3.77 \pm 0.08
J4	0.48 \pm 0.02	1.17 \pm 0.03	1.18 \pm 0.15	2.65 \pm 0.11	0.53 \pm 0.20
J5	0.19 \pm 0.23	0.54 \pm 0.25	1.15 \pm 0.70	0.89 \pm 0.28	0.22 \pm 0.81

Fig. 8. Kuka Youbot inverse kinematics in a circular trajectory (a) Without using mentioned Nearest Neighbour implementation. (b) Using mentioned Nearest Neighbour implementation.

C. Algorithm Count

The donut charts in Figures 9–12 illustrate the contribution of each algorithm in building datasets of size 10,000 for the four robots. For the KUKA YouBot (Fig 12) and the TM5-700 (Fig 11), the Nearest Neighbour (NN) approach dominated, contributing nearly the entire dataset (over 95%), while the metaheuristic algorithms accounted for only marginal fractions. This indicates that for smaller and more compact robots, NN-based solvers were more effective or favored during dataset construction, with population-based approaches playing only a minor role.

In contrast, the FANUC M-20iA (Fig 9) presented a more

balanced distribution. The NN method still provided the majority (around three-quarters of the dataset), but significant contributions came from Social Group Optimization (SGO) and the Genetic Algorithm (GA), with smaller yet meaningful shares from Differential Evolution (DE), Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), and Teaching–Learning Based Optimization (TLBO). This suggests that for mid-sized industrial manipulators, metaheuristics complemented NN more actively.

The most balanced outcome appeared in the Kawasaki BX200L (Fig 10), where NN contributed just over half of the dataset. SGO and GA provided substantial shares, while DE and PSO also played important roles. This reflects that

for larger robots with higher degrees of freedom and complex workspaces, metaheuristic search strategies became more essential, reducing dependence on NN.

Overall, the figures highlight a scaling trend: smaller robots rely heavily on Nearest Neighbour solutions, whereas larger robots generate new data points through increased involvement of metaheuristics. This aligns with the intuition that NN solvers excel in compact configuration spaces, while population-based algorithms provide better exploration for bigger landscapes.

Fig. 9. Donut chart showing the contribution of each algorithm in building a dataset of size 10,000 for the Fanuc M-20iA robot.

Fig. 10. Donut chart showing the contribution of each algorithm in building a dataset of size 10,000 for the Kawasaki BX200L robot.

Fig. 11. Donut chart showing the contribution of each algorithm in building a dataset of size 10,000 for the TM5-700 robot.

Fig. 12. Donut chart showing the contribution of each algorithm in building a dataset of size 10,000 for the KUKA YouBot robot.

D. Probability of KD-ADAM

The average time for a KD-tree query was measured at $6.13 \pm 0.73 \mu s$, which is significantly lower than the 50–100 ms required to execute metaheuristic methods, as mentioned in Table V – VIII. Consequently, the dataset generator should naturally favor the faster approach, a preference that is further supported by the probability-per-iteration values recorded in the generated dataset file.

The maximum reach radius of each robot can be approximated by summing the a and d parameters across all joints.

Fig. 13. Probability of selecting NN_Adam at a given dataset size for the Kawasaki BX200L.

Fig. 14. Probability of selecting NN_Adam at a given dataset size for the Fanuc M20iA.

Using the DH parameters from Table I – IV, the effective reach of the manipulators was estimated, which allows us to relate the probability of a nearest neighbour approach being selected to both the dataset size and the physical scale of the robots. The approximate maximum reach values sorted from largest to smallest are:

- Kawasaki BX200L: 1500 mm
- FANUC M-20iA: 1090 mm
- TM5-700: 640.5 mm
- KUKA YouBot: 323 mm

Larger manipulators cover wider workspaces, increasing the density of candidate configurations, while smaller robots limit neighbourhood size. As a result, the efficiency of nearest neighbour searches becomes particularly important for larger arms. For this study, the algorithm combines Nearest Neighbour search with post-processing using the Adam Optimiser, applied whenever a randomly generated point has a nearest neighbour within a 100 mm radius.

This difference in workspace and neighbourhood density is reflected in the probability per iteration for selecting a nearest neighbour, which varies with robot size. For the largest robot, the Kawasaki BX200L, Fig 13 shows an almost linear trend with a barely noticeable concavity, reaching approximately 0.3595 at 10,000 datapoints. The Fanuc M20iA, the second largest, displays a more pronounced concave curve in Fig 14, ending at around 0.6222. Smaller robots converge more quickly: for the TM5-700, the curve in Fig 15 approaches 1 after about 2,000 datapoints, reaching 0.9645 at 10,000. The smallest robot, the KUKA YouBot, demonstrates the general trend observed across all robots at large dataset sizes, as shown in Fig 16, converging near 1 with a final value of 0.9878 at the 10,000 datapoint mark.

E. KD Tree Rebuild Frequency

To benchmark data generation framework efficiency, 10,000 datapoints create runtimes were recorded for the Fanuc M20iA

Fig. 15. Probability of selecting NN_Adam at a given dataset size for the TM5-700.

with different KD-tree configurations. Without any KD-tree acceleration, it took 10040.77 ± 706.53 s (167 minutes) on average, confirming heavy inverse kinematics solving repetition computational cost. Incorporating KD-trees reduced the runtime by 11–16%, depending on the rebuild strategy. The standard rebuild policy, which reconstructs the KD-tree every 200 insertions, delivered the best performance with a runtime of 8415.94 ± 91.55 s (140 minutes). The balance-based rebuild policy followed with 8663.98 ± 144.10 s (144 minutes), and the no-rebuild policy averaged 8907.65 ± 347.07 s (148 minutes). The latter two indicated non-negligible overhead from rebuilding and balance calculation, and thus are less desirable compared to the standard policy with optimal performance. The findings indicate KD-trees not only accelerate data generation but maintain constant efficiency with different rebuilding schemes as well, and the approach can

Fig. 16. Probability of selecting NN_Adam at a given dataset size for the KUKA YouBot.

Fig. 17. Plot for balance score in no rebuild policy

transfer to other robotic platforms with little difficulty beyond the Fanuc M20iA.

If KD-trees grow sufficiently large, the chosen rebuilding strategy directly influences how often they must be reconstructed. The optimal query complexity in a balanced KD-tree is $O(\log_2 n)$, but it can degrade to $O(n)$ if rebalancing is neglected. As shown in Fig 17, the balance score drops below 0.2, introducing significant query overhead. In contrast, Fig 18 demonstrates that rebuilding every 200 iterations is well-suited for datasets of size 10,000, making it the most effective strategy in this setting. Meanwhile, Fig 19 highlights that a balance-score-driven rebuilding policy reduces the frequency of rebuilds as the dataset grows, suggesting that such an adaptive approach would scale better for sufficiently large datasets.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this work, FORGE, a modular hybrid framework for generating high-quality datasets for inverse kinematics learning in constrained and collision-prone environments, was introduced. By combining metaheuristic global search, using but not limited to 5 popular algorithms, GA, PSO, TLBO, DE, and SGO,

Fig. 18. Plot for balance score in regular rebuild policy

Fig. 19. Plot for balance score in balance-based rebuild policy

gradient-based refinement via the Adam optimizer, and efficient nearest-neighbour retrieval through KD-trees, FORGE effectively balanced positional accuracy, angular efficiency, and collision avoidance across multiple robotic platforms. Experiments on four manipulators—Kawasaki BX200L, Fanuc M20iA, TM5-700, and KUKA YouBot—demonstrated that the framework not only enhanced solution feasibility and achieved sub-millimeter precision but also significantly reduced dataset generation time. The evaluation encompassed multiple dimensions: accuracy improvements before and after Adam refinement, probability distribution analysis of joint configuration repeatability for identical target queries, comparative contributions of metaheuristics versus nearest-neighbour search in dataset construction, and the efficiency of different KD-tree rebuilding policies. These results highlight both the robustness and adaptability of FORGE to diverse robotic configurations and operating conditions.

Future research will extend FORGE towards integration with neural networks, as only a proof-of-concept exists so far, and no extensive analysis exists in this direction. Further investigations are encouraged to evaluate the framework with a wider range of metaheuristic algorithms and incorporate additional functionalities to improve performance and runtime efficiency. Expanding FORGE towards trajectory optimization would open a lot of pathways for the future. Another important direction is the deployment of FORGE on physical robotic platforms beyond simulation, enabling the assessment of its effectiveness and robustness in real-time, real-world environ-

ments.

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APPENDIX A CODE AVAILABILITY

To ensure reproducibility and facilitate further research, the complete implementation of the FORGE framework is publicly available via Zenodo [52].

APPENDIX B DATASET AVAILABILITY

To support reproducibility and facilitate data-driven evaluation, the IK-FORGE 2025 dataset is publicly available [53].